

CUSTOMER PROFILE AND THE ANALYSIS OF LOAN PRODUCTS AND SERVICES OFFERED BY UNIVERSAL BANKS IN CALBAYOG CITY, SAMAR

Fritz Jeffry Z. Briones, Rey James B. Roxas, Christopher D. Salino

Northwest Samar State University, Samar, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the customer profiles and the demand for loan products and services provided by universal banks in Calbayog City, Samar. As a significant component of the Philippine banking sector, universal banks offer a wide array of financial services, making them integral to the nation's economic growth. In employing a descriptive correlational research design, the study aimed to analyze the relationship between customer profiles—including age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, occupation, employer, monthly salary, and banking duration—and their preferences for various loan products and services. Data was collected from a purposively sampled population of 250 bank customers, using a researcher-made questionnaire, and was analyzed using statistical methods such as ANOVA and Pearson's correlation. The findings revealed that age, income, and transaction history with the bank are significant factors influencing customers' demand for specific loan services. Middle-aged, higher-income earners showed a preference for car loans with competitive interest rates, while long-term customers and married individuals were more inclined towards housing loans that offer stability and security. Business loans were primarily demanded by self-employed individuals, highlighting the need for personalized financial solutions. The study suggests that universal banks should tailor their marketing strategies and enhance digital services to cater to the diverse needs of their clientele. Recommendations for future research include expanding demographic scope and assessing the impact of digital banking on traditional service demand.

Keywords: *Universal banks, customer profile, loan products, loan services, marketing strategies*

INTRODUCTION

The banking sector is very important in driving the growth of economies as it offers key monetary services to all areas of the economy. For a bank to remain viable and successful over time, it must understand what its customers want and need so that it can respond through development of focused plans intended at improving levels clients' contentment while staying competitive. This paper examines the part played by universal banks that are now seen as crucial players in enhancing banking sector performance due to economies of scale and income diversification (Dayag, 2019).

Universal banks offer a comprehensive range of financial services, including retail, commercial, and investment services. This broad spectrum of services enables these banks to diversify risks and capitalize on economies of scope, particularly in information management (Akiyoshi, 2019). Such strategies are believed to enhance returns and create high-quality assets, safeguarding the interests of stakeholders in the banking industry (Dayag, 2019).

The correlation between the growth of universal banking and economic development has been a subject of interest. For instance, Dayag (2019) explored this relationship in the Philippines, highlighting how banks foster economic growth by facilitating business creation and expansion. Efficient fund allocation by banks is crucial for sustainable economic growth. In the context of the Philippines, the top five universal banks, according to the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas' records, are key players in this dynamic economic landscape (Yap-Virtudazo, 2020).

However, the banking sector faces challenges due to the integration of modern information technology and changes in consumer behavior. Fan (2023) points out that these developments have impacted traditional retail operations in banks and intensified competition in the retail sector. Banks are now compelled to revise their retail business marketing strategies and adapt to the evolving financial demands of consumers (Fan, 2023).

This study aimed to analyze the loan products and services demanded by customers of universal banks in Calbayog City, Samar. It seeks to formulate marketing strategies that align with customer preferences, focusing on loans – one of the two key areas of bank operations (Nguyen et al., 2018). Banks play a crucial role as intermediaries, managing deposits (input) and providing loans (output), which are central to their operations (Gobat, 2023). Understanding customer demands in these areas is vital for banks to remain relevant and competitive.

In order to understand how clients prefer banking services and what they require, an analysis was done on client's socio-economic and demographic characteristics. The purpose of this research is to determine customer preference and behaviour concerning universal banks in Calbayog City and covers several dimensions thereof. The primary objectives were to assess the demand for loan products and services, analyze how these

demands vary across different customer profiles, and identify any significant relationships between customer profiles and their banking preferences.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the products and services demanded by the customers of universal banks in Calbayog City, Samar with the end goal of formulating marketing strategies for banks.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

What is the extent of the demanded products and services of universal banks in Calbayog for loans?

1. How do these demands vary across different customer profiles?
2. Are there any significant relationships between customer profiles and their banking preferences?
3. What marketing strategies can be made based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research design with a focus on descriptive-quantitative methods, particularly descriptive correlational methods. This approach is suitable for identifying characteristics, frequencies, trends, correlations, and classifications of a specific subject. Descriptive-correlation methods, as detailed by Stangor and Walinga (2019), are used to collect data to assess the existence and strength of relationships between variables. In this study, this method was utilized to analyze the relationship between customers' profiles and their demands for products and services at universal banks in Calbayog City. The study targeted customers from Land Bank of the Philippines, Metropolitan Bank and Trust Company, Philippine National Bank, Rizal Commercial Banking Corporation, and United Coconut Planters Bank in Calbayog City. The distribution of respondents across these banks is shown in Table 1, with a total population size of 842 participants.

Table 1. Distribution of the Total Population of Respondents of the Study

Respondents	f	%
Land bank of the Philippines	169	20.07
Metropolitan Bank and Trust Company	169	20.07
Philippine National Bank	168	19.95
Rizal Commercial Banking Corp	168	19.95
United Coconut Planters Bank	168	19.95
TOTAL	842	100.00

Purposive sampling was employed to select 250 respondents, 50 from each bank, based on specific criteria (Creswell, 2014). These criteria included being a regular customer with at least one transaction every six months and maintaining an average daily

balance for a minimum of six months. A researcher-made questionnaire was used, comprising three parts: respondent profile, desired banking products and services, and issues encountered in transactions. The level of demand was gauged using a rating scale with both quantitative and qualitative values.

Validation of the Instrument

Content validation was conducted by a panel of experts at Northwest Samar State University, with the instrument undergoing revisions based on their feedback. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability Coefficient of Each Category of the Questionnaire

Category	Number of Items	Reliability Coefficient	Interpretation
Loan Products	4	0.80	Very Good Reliability
Loan Services	6	0.90	Excellent Reliability
Problems Encountered	13	0.79	Good Reliability
OVER-ALL	51	0.95	Excellent Reliability

Legend:

- 0.90 and above - Excellent Reliability
- 0.80 - 0.89 - Very Good Reliability
- 0.70 - 0.79 - Good Reliability
- 0.60 - 0.69 - Somewhat Low Reliability
- 0.50 - 0.59 - Needs Revision
- 0.49 and below - Questionable Items

Data was collected after obtaining approval from the bank managers. Data analysis utilized Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) and chi-square. These methods were used to analyze respondent profiles, assess demand for banking products and services, and explore relationships between customer profiles and their banking preferences.

RESULTS

Extent of Demand of the Universal Bank Loan Products and Services

Table 3 represents the mean and standard deviation on the extent of demand of loan products by the customer in the universal bank in Calbayog City. Understanding the importance of these loan products in customers' daily lives is crucial for banks to tailor their offerings and meet customers' financial needs effectively. The two loan products that have high level of demands are the following products: Car Loan and Business Loan.

1243

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent of Demand of the Loan Products by the Customers in the Universal Banks in Calbayog City

Loan Products	Mean	Description	SD
Car Loan	2.58	High	0.71
Housing Loan	2.50	Moderate	0.73
Business Loan	2.52	High	0.68
1 to 1(Loan VS Deposit)	2.20	Moderate	0.82

Legend:

- 2.51 – 3.00 - High
- 1.51 – 2.50 - Moderate
- 1.00 – 1.50 - Low

Two loan products have a high mean, indicating a high level of demand: "Car Loan" and "Business Loan." The high mean suggests that these loan products are sought after by customers and play a significant role in fulfilling their financial goals and aspirations. Banks should ensure the availability and accessibility of these loan products while maintaining competitive interest rates and flexible repayment terms. Additionally, banks can offer personalized loan packages and efficient application processes to enhance customer satisfaction and attract a larger customer base (Ismail et. al., 2018).

Two loan products have a moderate mean, signifying a moderate level of demand: "Housing Loan" and "1 to 1 (Loan VS Deposit)." While these loan products may not have the same level of demand as the ones with a high mean, they still hold importance for customers in meeting their housing and financial needs. Banks can focus on streamlining the application and approval processes for housing loans, providing competitive interest rates, and offering tailored loan options to cater to customers' diverse requirements (Dwivedi et. al., 2021). Similarly, for the "1 to 1 (Loan VS Deposit)" product, banks can highlight the benefits and convenience of this integrated loan and deposit service to attract customers seeking a holistic financial solution.

Understanding the extent of demand for loan products enables banks to align their loan portfolios and strategies with customer preferences and market trends (Choi, 2018). In focusing on highly demanded loan products, banks can capitalize on the opportunities presented by customers' financial needs and drive loan growth. For loan products with moderate demand, banks can explore targeted marketing efforts, educational campaigns, and enhanced customer engagement to increase awareness and adoption (Chen, 2020).

Table 4. Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent of Demand of the Loan Services by the Customers in the Universal Banks in Calbayog City

Loan Services	Mean	Description	SD
Sale of Acquired Properties	2.49	Moderate	0.80
Post Dated Check Warehousing	2.32	Moderate	0.85
Auto debit Facility	2.23	Moderate	0.82
Fire Insurance	2.27	Moderate	0.81
Car Insurance	2.24	Moderate	0.81
Domestic Bills Purchase	2.05	Moderate	0.90

All of the loan services listed in Table 4 have a moderate mean, indicating a moderate level of demand. This suggests that customers perceive these loan services as valuable and beneficial to their financial needs, although they may not have the same level of demand as services categorized as high. Banks can capitalize on this moderate demand by emphasizing the unique features and advantages of these loan services to attract more customers and enhance their overall banking experience (Chen, 2020).

The loan service "Sale of Acquired Properties" has a moderate mean, indicating that customers find value in this service, potentially for investment or property acquisition purposes. Banks can enhance their marketing efforts by providing comprehensive property listings, facilitating smooth transactions, and offering competitive financing options to cater to customers interested in this loan service (Fan, 2023).

"Post Dated Check Warehousing" and "Auto Debit Facility" also have a moderate mean, suggesting that customers value the convenience and efficiency of these services. Banks can focus on promoting the benefits of these services, such as streamlining payment processes, ensuring timely transactions, and reducing administrative burdens for customers. In highlighting the ease and reliability of these services, banks can attract more customers and differentiate themselves from competitors (Dwivedi et. al., 2021).

The loan services "Fire Insurance," "Car Insurance," and "Domestic Bills Purchase" also exhibit a moderate level of demand. These services are important for customers seeking insurance coverage for their properties, vehicles, and managing their domestic bill payments (Ramasamy, 2020). Banks can collaborate with reputable insurance providers to offer comprehensive insurance packages, competitive premiums, and hassle-free claims processes. Additionally, banks can develop user-friendly platforms and systems to facilitate convenient bill payments, ensuring a seamless banking experience for customers.

Analyzing the level of demand for loan services enables banks to fine-tune their service portfolio, pinpoint areas requiring enhancement, and improve overall customer satisfaction. In directing their attention to loan services with a moderate level of demand, banks can customize their approaches and allocate resources to deliver outstanding customer experiences. This entails optimizing operational processes, furnishing

customers with informative materials, and harnessing technology to augment accessibility and convenience (Reznik et. al., 2021). Consequently, banks can strengthen their competitive advantage by providing valuable loan services, fostering customer loyalty, and driving sustainable growth (Enad & Gerinda, 2022).

Test of Significant Difference on the Demand on Loan Products and Services of the Customers in the Universal Banks of Calbayog City

Table 5. Significant Difference on the Demand on Loan Services of the Customers in the Universal Banks of Calbayog City

Customer Profile	Car Loan (Demand)	Housing Loan (Demand)	Business Loan (Demand)	1 to 1 (Loan VS Deposit) (Demand)
Age	F = 5.973**	F = 6.448**	F = 7.948**	F = 6.933**
	df = 3, 164	df = 3, 169	df = 3, 152	df = 3, 132
	p = 0.001	p < 0.001	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
Sex	F = 1.746ns	F = 0.973ns	F = 0.801ns	F = 1.747ns
	df = 172	df = 177	df = 165	df = 138
	p = 0.083	p = 0.332	p = 0.424	p = 0.083
Civil Status (CS)	F = 1.783ns	F = 0.705ns	F = 0.907ns	F = 1.028ns
	df = 3, 168	df = 3, 173	df = 3, 162	df = 3, 136
	p = 0.152	p = 0.55	p = 0.439	p = 0.382
Highest Educational Attainment (HEA)	F = -2.730**	F = -0.872ns	F = -0.584ns	F = -2.632*
	df = 154	df = 161	df = 154	df = 125
	p = 0.007	p = 0.384	p = 0.56	p = 0.01
Occupation	F = 3.548**	F = 1.083ns	F = 1.030ns	F = 1.507ns
	df = 5, 164	df = 5, 169	df = 5, 157	df = 5, 131
	p = 0.005	p = 0.372	p = 0.402	p = 0.192
Employer	F = 6.699**	F = 2.981*	F = 4.060**	F = 2.325*
	df = 4, 167	df = 4, 173	df = 4, 160	df = 5, 134
	p < 0.001	p = 0.021	p = 0.004	p = 0.046
Monthly Salary	F = 5.542**	F = 5.026**	F = 5.502**	F = 6.708**
	df = 4, 167	df = 4, 172	df = 4, 161	df = 4, 135
	p < 0.001	p = 0.001	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
Occupation	F = 3.548**	F = 1.083ns	F = 1.030ns	F = 1.507ns
	df = 5, 164	df = 5, 169	df = 5, 157	df = 5, 131
Number of Years Transacting with the Bank	F = 2.266ns	F = 4.094**	F = 1.646ns	F = 1.031ns

	df = 4, 159	df = 4, 163	df = 4, 152	df = 4, 126
	p = 0.064	p = 0.003	p = 0.166	p = 0.394

Legend:

- ** - Highly Significant at 0.05 level
- * - Significant at 0.05 level
- ns - Not Significant

All listed loan products including "Car Loan," "Housing Loan," "Business Loan," and "1 to 1 (Loan VS Deposit)" showed highly significant differences in demand based on monthly salary. This indicates that customers' monthly salary levels significantly impact their preferences and demand for different loan products. The "Housing Loan" was the only loan product that exhibited highly significant differences based on the number of years transacting, suggesting that customers' preferences for housing loans evolve as their relationship with the bank matures. However, other loan products such as "Car Loan," "Business Loan," and "1 to 1 (Loan VS Deposit)" did not show significant differences in demand based on the number of years transacting.

Particularly, the strong correlation between monthly salary and loan demand across all products indicates that financial capacity plays a pivotal role in customers' borrowing behaviors. This finding aligns with Lyons et. al. (2019), who found that income levels significantly influence loan uptake, as higher-income individuals are more likely to invest and seek financial leverage. Additionally, the significant relationship between the duration of a banking relationship and the demand for housing loans underscores the importance of customer loyalty and long-term engagement for more substantial financial commitments. This observation is supported by Sani et. al. (2022), who noted that trust built over time with a financial institution significantly affects customers' willingness to engage in long-term loan services. The absence of a similar trend for other loan types may suggest that such products are more influenced by immediate financial needs rather than the depth of the banking relationship, a notion that Kenttä et. al. (2022) suggests in their study on consumer borrowing patterns. These findings underscore the necessity for banks to tailor their marketing and customer service strategies according to the diverse financial states and transaction histories of their clientele, ensuring that the right products are offered to the right customers at the right time.

Table 8. Significant Difference on the Demand on Loan Services of the Customers in the Universal Banks of Calbayog City

Customer Profile	Loan Services	Sale of Acquired Properties	Post Dated Check Warehousing	Auto debit Facility	Fire Insurance	Car Insurance	Domestic Bills Purchase
Age	F-value	5.361**	7.800**	11.642**	7.648**	1.917ns	5.615**
	df	3, 153	3, 149	3, 144	3, 133	3, 132	3, 109

	p-value	0.002	0	0	0	0.13	0.001
Sex	F-value	0.908ns	0.775ns	1.412ns	1.529ns	-0.671ns	0.771ns
	df	160	155	151	140	140	114
	p-value	0.365	0.44	0.16	0.128	0.503	0.442
CS	F-value	2.981*	1.410ns	0.715ns	0.306ns	0.394ns	0.369ns
	df	3, 158	3, 153	3, 148	3, 138	3, 138	3, 112
	p-value	0.033	0.242	0.544	0.821	0.757	0.776
HEA	F-value	-2.741**	-1.499ns	-0.987ns	-1.176ns	-0.493ns	-0.171ns
	df	146	142	138	129	128	107
	p-value	0.007	0.136	0.325	0.242	0.623	0.865
Occupation	F-value	2.732*	0.910ns	0.510ns	1.037ns	1.121ns	0.732ns
	df	4, 154	5, 148	5, 144	5, 133	5,133	5107
	p-value	0.031	0.476	0.768	0.399	0.352	0.601
Employer	F-value	2.938*	3.034*	3.775*	2.602*	3.620**	1.061ns
	df	5, 156	5, 151	5, 147	5, 136	5, 136	5, 110
	p-value	0.015	0.012	0.003	0.028	0.004	0.386
Monthly Salary	F-value	5.263**	6.190**	13.139**	7.127**	2.438*	5.016**
	df	4, 157	4, 152	4, 148	4, 136	4, 136	4, 111
	p-value	0.001	0	0	0	0.05	0.001
Number of Years Transacting with the Bank	F-value	2.895*	2.725*	4.857*	4.011**	2.029ns	4.153**
	df	4149	4143	4140	4129	429	4104
	p-value	0.024	0.032	0.001	0.004	0.094	0.004

In terms of loan services, significant differences based on the number of years transacting were observed for "Auto Debit Facility," "Fire Insurance," "Sale of Acquired Properties," and "Post Dated Check Warehousing." This indicates that as customers engage with the bank for a longer period, their preferences for these loan services evolve. However, "Car Insurance" did not exhibit significant differences in demand based on the number of years transacting, suggesting that customers' preferences for this service remain relatively stable.

The results outlined in Table 8 highlight a discernible pattern wherein the duration of the customer's relationship with the bank directly influences the demand for certain

loan services, such as "Auto Debit Facility," "Fire Insurance," "Sale of Acquired Properties," and "Post Dated Check Warehousing." This tendency may reflect a growing confidence and familiarity with the bank's offerings, or an increased appreciation for the convenience and security these services provide as reported in studies by Jain et. al. (2023). These findings could imply that long-term customers develop a more sophisticated understanding of their financial needs and the bank's capacity to fulfill them, echoing the sentiments found Albarq's (2023) research on consumer-bank relationships. On the other hand, the stable demand for "Car Insurance" regardless of the transaction history with the bank could indicate that the need for this service is perceived as fundamental and immediate, similar to the observations made by Meral & Sener (2022) in their study on insurance product uptake. The implications of these results are significant for banks, as they suggest a need to develop dynamic marketing strategies and customer service approaches that evolve with the customer's tenure, leveraging insights from both behavioral finance and long-term relationship management as supported by Gonu et al. (2023).

DISCUSSIONS

Marketing Strategies for Loan Products and Services Based on the Findings

Table 9 presents tailored marketing strategies for a range of loan products and services offered by Universal Banks in Calbayog City, designed to meet the specific needs of various target demographics based on the empirical findings of the study.

Table 9. Marketing Strategies for Loan Products and Services in Universal Banks of Calbayog City

Loan Product/Service	Target Demographic	Marketing Strategy
Car Loan	Middle-aged, higher income earners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight competitive interest rates, flexible repayment plans • Use digital marketing to showcase ease of application and approval processes.
Housing Loan	Long-term bank customers, married individuals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasize the stability and security of owning a home. • Offer tailored loan options and efficient processing for existing customers.
Business Loan	Self-employed, business owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase success stories of businesses that benefited from loans. • Provide personalized financial advice and support.

1 to 1 (Loan VS Deposit)	Customers with consistent banking relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote as a comprehensive financial management tool. • Highlight benefits for customers with regular transactions and deposits.
Sale of Acquired Properties	Investment-focused customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use targeted advertising to showcase available properties. • Offer seminars or webinars on the benefits of property investment.
Post Dated Check Warehousing	Customers with substantial transactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create educational content on managing financial obligations and cash flow. • Offer demonstrations of how warehousing can simplify business transactions.
Auto Debit Facility	Busy professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the convenience and time-saving aspects. • Use email marketing and online platforms to explain the process and benefits.
Fire Insurance and Car Insurance	Loan customers, property and vehicle owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bundle insurance with relevant loans. • Provide clear information on coverage benefits and claim processes. • Use customer testimonials to build trust.
Domestic Bill Purchase	High-balance account holders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personalized outreach to high-value customers to explain benefits. • Use case studies to demonstrate how it can aid in financial management.

Conclusions

The study has demonstrated that Universal Banks in Calbayog City have a diverse customer base with distinct demands for loan products and services. Middle-aged, higher-income earners are drawn to competitive interest rates and flexible repayment options for car loans, while long-term bank customers and married individuals seek stability and security in housing loans. Business loans are popular among self-employed individuals, who value personalized financial advice and success stories from their peers. The

1250

demand for the "1 to 1 (Loan VS Deposit)" service underscores the importance of comprehensive financial management tools for customers with consistent banking relations. Investment-focused customers are interested in the sale of acquired properties, and customers with substantial transactions benefit from services like Post Dated Check Warehousing and Auto Debit Facility. Insurance products are crucial for loan customers who seek to protect their assets, whereas high-balance account holders show a preference for services that aid in sophisticated financial management. Banks may continue to tailor their product offerings and marketing strategies to the needs of their varied customer profiles, emphasizing the benefits aligned with their financial behaviors and preferences.

Recommendations

To address the study's limitations, further research should explore a broader demographic to confirm these findings across different regions. Additionally, future studies could investigate the impact of digital banking trends on customer preferences and the demand for traditional banking services. For practical applications, banks are advised to invest in customer education programs to enhance financial literacy, particularly among customers new to banking services. This could improve the uptake of more complex banking products and services. Furthermore, banks should consider enhancing their digital platforms to meet the growing demand for convenient and rapid banking transactions. Finally, it is recommended that future studies examine the long-term impacts of these marketing strategies on customer satisfaction and bank performance, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of tailored marketing approaches in the banking sector.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered to strict ethical standards to ensure the integrity of the study and the welfare of the participants. Approval for the study was obtained from the ethics review board of Northwest Samar State University. All participants provided informed consent before participating in the study, with assurances of confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. The research design and methods were conducted in accordance with established ethical guidelines, ensuring that no harm came to the participants and that their rights and dignity were respected throughout the research process.

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